

2. Close-up of typical *S. oryzae* symptoms on sheaths of *E. colona*.

Although the fungus is known to be seedborne, how the infection initiates from the infected seeds is unknown. Perhaps *E. colona* is the alternate host of *S. oryzae*. It may be responsible for spreading inocula to healthy rice plants during panicle initiation to boot stages, when the plants are thought to be infected.

This is the first report of an alternate host of *S. oryzae*. We suggest *E. colona* be destroyed around levees, fields, and areas adjacent to rice production to avoid the disease. The weed not only hosts *S. oryzae* but also other disease organisms, including rice tungro virus. *h*

Seed treatment as prophylaxis against root-knot nematode in rice

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We tested the efficacy of treating rice seed (variety Ratna) with common fungicides to deter root invasion and endoparasite development of rice root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*. Seeds were treated with a 3:1000 fungicide solution applied at 3 g/kg seed

before planting them in pots. Soil was inoculated with second-stage infective nematode larvae (60 larvae/g soil). Seedlings were examined for root-knot and endoparasitic stages of the nematode 30 days after germination. Treatments were replicated four times.

Ceresan dry, a mercurial seed dressing fungicide recommended for control of rice blast, Helminthosporiose, and foot rot was most effective (see table). Seed treatment was effective against fungal diseases and nematodes. *h*

Effect of fungicidal seed treatment on rice nematode control, Orissa, India.

Fungicide	Chemical name	No. of female larvae/plant root system
Blitox-50	Copper oxychloride	20.25
Captafol	N-[(1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethyl) sulphenyl-cis-4-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboximide]	25.20
Ziram	Zn-dimethyl dithiocarbamate	23.30
Coppesan 45.5 wp	Copper oxychloride	29.15
Mancozeb	Zn-ethylene-bis + manganous ethylene-bis dithiocarbamate	26.30
Carbendazim	2-(methoxy-carbamoyl) benzimidazole	25.95
Ceresan dry	Ethyl mercury chloride	12.95
Control		26.55
C.D. (0.01)		10.20

Efficacy of fungicides for the control of brown spot

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Rice brown spot caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan (*Cochliobolus miyabeanus* Ito et Kurib) is a serious disease in Uttar Pradesh and other Indian rice-growing states. Because primary infection is from seed and secondary infection from airborne inoculum, researchers theorized that a seed treatment followed by foliar fungicidal application might effectively control the disease.

Five seed dressing and seven foliar fungicides (Tables 1 and 2) were tested for ability to control brown spot. Field

Table 1. Relative efficacy of seed dressing fungicides on grain infection and paddy yield.

Fungicide (2.5 g/kg)	Grain infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Mancozeb	5.82	3.0
Thiram	4.47	2.6
Blitox	7.21	2.2
Ceresan	9.23	2.1
Tillex	8.45	2.0
Control	12.11	1.5
C.D. (5%)	1.30	1.40

Table 2. Effect of fungicidal foliar spray on grain infection and paddy yield.

Fungicide	Dose (%)	Grain infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Mancozeb	0.30	4.62	3.0
Kitazin 48%	0.10	5.78	2.7
Blitox	0.25	5.10	2.4
Blue copper	0.30	7.17	2.3
Zineb	0.30	6.12	2.2
Dithane-C-10	0.30	5.89	2.3
Captafol	0.30	8.02	2.1
Control		14.62	1.9
C.D. (5%)		3.30	4.16

tests using a split-plot design and three replications were conducted during the 1977-78 wet season. Jhona 349 was the susceptible variety. Seeds were treated with fungicides before sowing. Foliage was sprayed 25, 40, 55, and 70 days after transplanting.

Grain infection was lowest when seeds were dressed with thiram and mancozeb.

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